

Title: Pupillary and attentional responses to infant facial expressions in mothers across socioeconomic variations

Authors: Santeri Yrttiaho, Belinda Bruwer, Heather J. Zar, Kirsten A Donald, Susan Malcolm-Smith, Lee Ginton, Nadia Hoffman, Eileen Vuong, Dana Niehaus, Jukka M. Leppänen, Dan J. Stein

Abstract: Maternal responses to infant facial expressions were examined in two socioeconomically diverse samples of South African mothers (Study I, N = 111; and Study II, N = 214). Responses were measured by using pupil and gaze tracking. Study I showed increased pupil response to infant distress expressions in groups recruited from private as compared to public maternity clinics, possibly reflecting underlying differences in socioeconomic status (SES) across the groups. Study II, sampling uniformly low SES neighborhoods, found increased pupil dilation and faster orientation to expressions of infant distress, but only in the highest income group. These results are consistent with maternal physiological and attentional sensitivity to infant distress cues but challenge the universality of this sensitivity across socioeconomic diversity.

Introduction

Infants communicate their internal states with variable gestures, vocalizations and facial expressions, are sensitive to the impact of these cues on maternal behavior, and generate internal models of mother's responses to expressed affect, activities, and needs (Feldman, 2007; Leclère et al., 2014). Although this learning takes place over time and repeated experience, the dyadic processes during the sensitive periods during the first year(s) of life are thought to be particularly influential for subsequent socioemotional development (Nelson et al., 2007).

Parental response to infant distress cues is an evolutionarily conserved (Bornstein, Putnick, Park, Suwalsky, & Haynes, 2017; Preston, 2013) and a tractable exemplar for inquiry into early parent-infant communication and its significance for child development and well-being. Maternal responsiveness to infant distress communication has been mostly studied through observational and questionnaire measures (Biringen, 2008), but recent studies have shown that infant distress cues elicit neural (Riem, van IJzendoorn, De Carli, Vingerhoets, & Bakermans-Kranenburg, 2017a; Riem, van IJzendoorn, De Carli, Vingerhoets, & Bakermans-Kranenburg, 2017b), electrocortical (Peltola et al., 2014), autonomic (Leerkes et al., 2015; Yrttiaho, Niehaus, Thomas, & Leppänen, 2017), and attentional (Thompson-Booth et al., 2014) signatures in adults that can be reliably assessed with more objective techniques. The results from these studies converge to show heightened neural and behavioral responses to infant faces expressing distressed affect in comparison to infant neutral or positive expressions. Studies comparing adults' responses to infant and adult distress cues have further shown that neural responses in the visual areas are stronger to infant as compared to adult distress cues [i.e., tears or sad faces, (Colasante, Mossad, Dudek, & Haley, 2017; Riem et al., 2017a; Riem, van IJzendoorn et al., 2017b)]. Responsiveness to infant faces expressing distress has been found in both parents and non-parents (Riem et al., 2017a; Riem, van IJzendoorn et al., 2017b), but there are also

indications that this response is more pronounced in mothers than in nulliparous women (Thompson-Booth et al., 2014) or in mothers, than in non-parent controls of both genders (Proverbio, Brignone, Matarazzo, Del Zotto, & Zani, 2006; Thompson-Booth et al., 2014).

Enhanced pupil dilation (Yrttiaho et al., 2017) and attentional orienting (Thompson-Booth et al., 2014) to infant distress cues may indicate adaptive processes that facilitate prompt responding to biologically significant signals. Pupil dilation has been associated with the activity of the noradrenergic system originating in the locus-coeruleus, the LC-NE system (Joshi, Li, Kalwani, & Gold, 2016; Laeng, Sirois, & Gredeback, 2012). The LC-NE system has neuromodulatory effects across cerebral and brainstem networks of attention, suggesting it has an essential role in selective weighting of sensory input and attention allocation (Reimer et al., 2014; Sara & Bouret, 2012; Wang, Boehnke, White, & Munoz, 2012). Individual differences in the pupil response have been reported in relation to difficulties in both attentional (Wainstein et al., 2017) and emotional (Cascardi, Armstrong, Chung, & Paré, 2015; Kimble, Fleming, Bandy, Kim, & Zambetti, 2010) regulation, and in psychiatric disorders (Granholm, Ruiz, Gallegos-Rodriguez, Holden, & Link, 2016; Naegeli et al., 2018; Siegle, Granholm, Ingram, & Matt, 2001). The direction of an individual's eye gaze, in turn, provides a direct, objective, and temporally intricate measure of the allocation of attention (Bannerman, Milders, & Sahraie, 2009; Hood & Atkinson, 1993; Leppänen et al., 2011; Nummenmaa, Hyönä, & Calvo, 2009). Therefore, the application of these tools in the study of adults' responses to infant emotions may provide a novel approach for describing individual differences in parenting behaviors, their origins, and functional significance.

Despite the rigor of the studies using objective techniques to examine parents' responses to infant emotions, this body of work has two major limitations. First, the majority of studies documenting enhanced physiological and attentional responsiveness to infant facial distress

cues have been conducted in Europe, North America, and Japan, reflecting a “sampling bias” with reliance on data from “western, educated, industrialized, rich, and democratic” (WEIRD) populations (Henrich, Heine, & Norenzayan, 2010). Second, there has been little research examining whether responsiveness to infant distress cues is associated with maternal mental health.

Several lines of research suggest that parental responses to infant cues may vary at individual (Barrett & Fleming, 2011), socioeconomic (Kim, Capistrano, & Congleton, 2016), and cultural (Bornstein et al., 2017) levels. In general, the influences of socio-economic status (SES) and culture have been proposed to converge via processes where available resources shape practices and behaviors that constitute culture (Kraus, Piff, & Keltner, 2011). Low-SES has been associated with external (vs. internal) cognitive attribution, other-oriented (vs. self-oriented) emotion, and engaged (vs. disengaged) social behavior [although opposite effects on cooperative behavior have also been found (Holland, Silva, & Mace, 2012; Nettle, Colléony, & Cockerill, 2011)]. Correspondingly, parenting that emphasizes dyadic, distal face-to-face interactions, thus fostering independence and agency of the young, may be neither valued or adaptive in non-western settings, including rural living, low formal education, material deprivation or insecurity, and living in extended families (Dawson, Bain, & Mesman, 2018; Hruschka, Munira, Jesmin, Hackman, & Tiokhin, 2018; Keller et al., 2018). Instead, one that promotes fitting in to a social group and a relational sense of the self, and which includes physical proximity with multiple caregivers appears more typical in many non-western cultures (Morelli et al., 2018). We suggest that mothering behaviors, including the processes that mediate enhanced responsiveness to infant distress cues, may covary with the differing parenting behaviors across socioeconomic strata and cultures.

In addition to variations across SES and cultures, there has been insufficient attention to the potential variations in maternal responsiveness in the context of mental health problems, which are more common during pregnancy and early post-natal periods and in low- and middle-income countries (Du Toit, Jordaan, Niehaus, Koen, & Leppanen, 2018). It is unclear how responsiveness is associated with mental health, but existing evidence points to bidirectional effects, characterized by hypo- or hyper-responsiveness to distress cues. Hyporesponsiveness is predicted by data suggesting that high personal stress may impede an individual's ability to focus on the needs of others (Eisenberg & Eggum, 2008; Leerkes et al., 2015). Conversely, overactive physiological responsiveness to infant distress has been identified as a correlate of abusive parenting (Joosen, Mesman, Bakermans-Kranenburg, & van Ijzendoorn, 2013), or neglect (Leerkes et al., 2015). These studies suggest the utility of such objective measures for studying the relationship between maternal responsiveness and mental health. It is of important note, however, that both maternal well-being and positive parenting behaviors are the outcome of multiple interconnected factors including perceived social support and specific internal resources that promote maternal resilience to emotional risk factors (Taylor & Conger, 2017). Therefore, the quality of parenting should not be viewed as being solely determined by maternal mental or physical health.

Our work in diverse samples of South African mothers provides a unique opportunity to address the two limitations of the literature examining maternal responsiveness to infant distress cues. In this exploratory study, we compared individual differences in responsiveness to infant distress cues in relation to socioeconomic variations (measured by separate variables for income, education, and employment, as well as assets in Study II) and mental health in ethnically diverse samples characterized by large variations in SES and mental health. The analyses were conducted in two separate samples to examine the generalizability of the

associations across samples and potential linkages between SES, mental health, and other, uncontrolled variations (e.g., residential location, ethnicity).

Based on the previous findings linking maternal responsiveness to SES, personal emotional risks, material deprivation, and cultural practices, we propose two broad but alternative hypotheses. The first is based on the concept of universal maternal responsiveness (Keller et al., 2018; Mesman, 2018). According to this hypothesis, relatively similar responsiveness would be predicted across heterogeneous groups despite socioeconomic and cultural variability, but the strength of the response to infant distress may be associated with personal emotional risks related here to mental disorders. The second hypothesis contrasts the universality hypothesis, and suggests that responsiveness differs across groups of people that are characterized by distinct socioeconomic and cultural settings indexed here by objective measures of SES. The hypotheses were formulated as non-directional as the studied independent factors have been previously associated with both decreased and exaggerated emotional responsiveness in indices ranging from brain activation (Kim et al., 2016) to autonomic arousal (Joosen et al., 2013; Leerkes et al., 2015) and observable behavior (Keller et al., 2018). The hypotheses were tested in two studies. Study I included participants from two clinics located at socioeconomically low and high residential areas, allowing us to i) examine whether the enhanced response to infant distress generalizes across societal and ethnic groups and ii) obtain preliminary data regarding how this response is associated with SES and mental health. Because the sample in Study I was highly stratified and did not represent a continuum from low to high SES or mental health variations, we extended the analyses to a second, more homogeneous sample (Study II), recruited from a single low to medium SES residential area.

Study I

Methods

Participants

Mothers of 6-week-old infants were recruited from a private clinic "blinded-for-review" and a public, state-funded clinic "blinded-for-review" as a part of an ongoing longitudinal study on maternal mental health in the "blinded-for-review" metropolitan area, South Africa. These two study sites serve different socio-economic groups, where the former serves predominantly clients with middle to high SES and the latter clients with low SES, in relation to local standards. The mothers were of Caucasian (53%), Black (31%), or of Mixed ancestry (14%). All participants who enrolled in the longitudinal study between June 5, 2014 and July 30, 2015 were included in the current analyses. The study was approved by the institutional review board of the University "blinded-for-review" and written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Further details of the sample can be found in the Supplementary Material.

Data from 111 mothers [age: $M (SD) = 32.4 (5.1)$ years] were included in the final analyses. Data from an additional 6 mothers were excluded due to insufficient data from the pupillometric assessment ($N = 2$) or missing data on some of the independent variables ($N = 4$).

Pupil responses to infant facial expressions

Stimuli: The stimuli were static pictures of infant faces displaying mild positive (MP), strong positive (SP), mild negative/distress (MN), and strong negative/distress (SN) emotional expressions (Figure 1). They were selected as a subset ($N=36$) from a larger pre-existing and validated database of emotional infant faces (Proverbio, Matarazzo, Brignone, Del Zotto, & Zani, 2007). In line with the validation of the entire stimulus database with respect to primary

dimensions of hedonic pleasure and arousal (Proverbio et al., 2007) analyses of behavioral responses to the selected 36 images have showed that the strong positive faces were predominantly judged as “happy”, mild positive as “neutral”, and both mild and strong negative as “sad” in a three-alternative forced choice classification task (Yrttiaho et al., 2017). For further details of the stimulus material, the reader is referred to a previous study using the same stimulus material (Yrttiaho et al., 2017) as well as to the construction and validation of the source image database (Proverbio et al., 2006; Proverbio et al., 2007).

***Please, insert Figure 1 around here. ***

Procedure: Pupil assessment was conducted at the infant age of 6 weeks, and as part of a scheduled immunization visit (for logistical convenience). In the pupil measurement, participant mothers were presented with sequences of stimuli on a black background, consisting of 1) a 1000-ms foreperiod with black screen and a sound “alarm” in the middle of this period, 2) a 2000-ms pre-stimulus interval with a visual noise stimulus, and 3) a 5000-ms face stimulus. The noise stimulus was created by randomizing the pixels of the face stimuli and was presented to minimize the luminance change (and related pupil constriction) for the onset of the face stimulus. The order of face stimuli was randomly shuffled for each participant. The measurement consisted of 36 trials corresponding to the equal number of face stimuli which were shuffled across the trials.

Acquisition and analysis of pupil diameter data: Pupil size was measured throughout the stimulus sequence with a Tobii X-60 or X2-60 eye-tracker camera (at 60 Hz) which measures corneal reflection of infrared light relative to the image of the pupil (N = 56 and 55, for X-60 and X2-60, respectively). The eye-trackers were swapped between the two data collection sites halfway through data collection in order to counterbalance between any confounding effects due to the tracker type.

Pupil analyses were conducted automatically using gazeAnalysisLib libraries (Leppänen, Forssman, Kaatiala, Yrttiaho, & Wass, 2015) in Matlab (Mathworks, Natick, MA, USA) and a priori set of parameters described by Yrttiaho et al. (2017). The preprocessing of pupil data included averaging of pupil size across the left and the right eye, data interpolation to replace missing frames, median filtering, and subtracting the 300-ms prestimulus baseline from the pupil response. The pupil dilation was extracted as the mean baseline-corrected pupil size during the time-window spanning 4000–5000 ms after face onset. During this window, the pupil typically dilated up to or above the 300-ms baseline period after an initial pupil constriction elicited by face onset (Figure 2).

The criteria for data quality for pupil tracking were established based on a previous study on emotional pupil response (Yrttiaho et al., 2017), which indicated a small but distinct class of trials with invalid eye-tracking or participant inattention. Following the criteria, we rejected trials where participant's gaze was diverted away from the face stimulus or the duration of interruptions in valid eye-tracking exceeded 250 ms or 900 ms during the time-windows for baseline or pupil dilation, respectively.

***Please, insert Figure 2 around here. ***

SES and mental health

SES was assessed separately within three subdomains including self-reported monthly family income (<ZAR10,000; ZAR10,000–20,000; ZAR20,000–40,000; >ZAR40,000), maternal education (0 = limited to primary or secondary school, 1 = higher education), and employment (0 = unemployed, 1 = employed/maternity leave/self-employed/housewife). Diagnostic interviews were performed by a psychiatrist using the Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview [MINI (Sheehan et al., 1998); version 6.0]. Finally, self-reported measures were collected on symptoms of maternal depression [EPDS (Choi et al., 2012)], problems in mother-infant bonding or attachment [MIBS, PBQ, and MPAS (Van Bussel, Spitz, & Demyttenaere, 2010)], and recent stressful life events [RLEQ questionnaire (Brugha, Bebington, Tennant, & Hurry, 1985)].

Statistical analyses

We extracted the emotional pupil response as the difference between pupil dilation in response to emotionally negative vs. positive stimuli. Individual differences in pupil responses were studied in relation to SES and psycho-social variables by comparing these variables across two distinct subsamples of participants recruited from high- and low-SES populations (N = 58, N =

53), respectively. This sample size was sufficient to detect effects of medium size ($d = 0.50$) within each sample and between the samples ($d = 0.54$) with t-tests.

Results

SES and mental health

Participants from the two distinct communities recruited in the study differed on all socioeconomic measures ($X^2s > 77.65, ps < .001$). In the public health care sample, most participants were from the lowest family income category (77%), had low level of education (89% had primary or at most secondary education), and were unemployed (89%). In contrast, the participants recruited from the private clinic were predominately from the highest family income category (71%), had a high level of education (95% had tertiary or other education), and were on maternity leave from their employment (83%). Distribution of SES variables across sites are indicated in Table I.

***Please, insert Table I around here. ***

Participants in the private clinic sample were on average 4 years older than public health care participants [$F(1,110) = 16.26, p < .001$]. Higher age was associated with higher educational

level in both groups [$F(1,110) = 4.70, p < .05, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .04$], but the differences between the two samples in SES variables remained after controlling for participants' age ($ps < .001$) by adding age as covariate in multivariate GLM.

The majority of participants across the two samples ($N = 83, 75\%$) had no diagnosed mental disorder, 20 were diagnosed with primary mood disorder, 3 with obsessive-compulsive disorder, 2 with anxiety disorders, and 6 with schizophrenia or a schizoaffective disorder. The prevalence of any mental disorder was higher in the public clinic sample (35.8%) than in the private clinic sample (15.5%; $\chi^2 = 6.07, p < .05$). The most severe mental disorders (psychotic disorders or major mood disorders, $N = 15$) were exclusively found in the public clinic sample. The number of adverse life-events reported was likewise higher in participants from the public [$M (SD) = 4.3 (3.7)$ events] than from the private clinic [2.6 (2.1) events; $F(1,110) = 8.42, p < .01$]. Finally, the number of participants with EPDS score above clinical threshold (Choi et al., 2012) was higher in the public health care sample (26.4%) than in the private clinic sample (5.2%, $\chi^2 = 9.64, p < .01$). Psychiatric morbidity and psychosocial self-reported scores across the two samples are indicated in Table II.

Pupil response

In the entire sample, an increase in pupil dilation (Figure 2) in response to pictures of infant negative vs. positive affect was on average 0.11 mm ($SD = .09$ mm) [$t(110) = 13.30, p < .001, d = 1.26$]. This emotional pupil response was found in both study samples [public clinic: $t(52) = 7.55, p < .001, d = 1.05$; private clinic: $t(57) = 12.32, p < .001; d = 1.62$]. However, the response was reduced in size for the public clinic sample (0.08 mm), as compared to the private clinic sample [0.14 mm; $F(1,108) = 16.82, p < .001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = .14$]. This inter-group effect

was controlled for the age difference between the samples by adding age as a covariate in multivariate GLM. No effect of age on the emotional pupil response was found [$F(1,108) = 0.02, p = .90$].

As two different eye trackers were used in Study I, we conducted further analyses to assess whether this might have influenced the emotional pupil measures. The use of the two trackers was not significantly associated with the sub-samples [$X^2=3.94, p = .14$] and the tracker type had no main or interaction effects on pupil response [$F_s < 3.01, p_s > .08$]. The effect of clinic site on emotional pupil response was found also when tracker type was added as a covariate [$F(1,104) = 10.10, p < .01$]

Pairwise correlations among study variables both across and within the two clinic samples are shown in Supplementary material (Tables SI-III). No associations between mental illness and pupil response was found within either of the study samples.

Study II

Methods

Participants

Participants were mother-infant dyads from the "blinded-for-review" study (references "blinded-for-review"), where the children were 3-years old children at inclusion, between July 6, 2016 and December 12, 2017. The participants were from a low-income residential area and of black (48%) and mixed (52%) ancestry. Altogether 222 mothers participated in the eye-tracking (ET) assessments of pupil and saccadic responses with 215 completing the data collection (in one or more of these assessments). Independent variables including SES,

psychiatric, and mental health data were available from 214 of these participants. The average age of the completers was 27.0 (SD = 5.8) years. No difference between ET completers and non-completers was found in any independent variables of the study [Multivariate $F_s(9, 202) < 1.53$; $p_s > .13$]. After quality control, data on pupil response, attention orientation to cued locations, and disengagement latency, was available from 190, 164, and 110 participants, respectively. Missing values within study variables were replaced using multiple imputation (see Statistical analyses, for further details). The acquired sample was sufficiently powered to detect small to medium associations, between independent variables and the eye-tracking-based measures, of $r(214) \geq .19$. Detailed diagram of data selection process is included in the Supplementary Material (Figure S1).

The study was approved by the ethical committee of the University "blinded-for-review" and written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Pupillary and orientation responses to infant facial expressions

Stimuli: The stimuli were selected from the same set of photographic stimuli of infant faces as in Study I. In Study I, the difference in pupil dilation was largest for strong negative (SN) vs. mild positive (MP) faces. To focus on this response and to reduce the number of stimulus conditions for Study II, we included only SN and MP faces in Study II.

Each face stimulus was preceded by a baseline stimulus to minimize changes in luminance at face onset and, as a result, the luminance-related pupil response. The baseline stimuli (Figure 1) were generated by randomly permuting the pixels of the face pictures within square-shaped bounding areas spanning the entire bitmap.

Procedure: Pupil responses were recorded for four different SN and four different MP faces. The participants viewed each of the faces three times (in three separate blocks), resulting in pupillary time series for a total of 12 SN and 12 MP stimuli.

Visual orientation to SN and MP faces was assessed by using two saccadic reaction time (SRT) tasks. The stimuli in these tasks were checkerboard patterns and five instances of SN and MP faces from the same set of infant faces as in the pupil measurement. Participant gaze was monitored with a Tobii X2-60 eye-tracker, and the acquired signal, consisting of point-of-gaze data, was preprocessed by median filtering, combining data across eyes, and extrapolating missing frames. Across both tasks, trials were rejected if the duration of interruptions in eye-tracking signal exceeded 200 ms or if the gaze was diverted from the initial target of fixation at the beginning of the trial. A minimum number of three trials was required from participants to be included in further analyses. SRT was determined as time elapsed from the onset of the lateral target stimulus to the time gaze left from the central fixation to the lateral target.

In the first SRT task, “Spatial association paradigm”, distinct spatial locations were associated with particular emotional expressions. This association was formed by presenting the infant face stimuli at the specified location which was at the left or the right side of the computer display. During each trial, participants were first presented with a flickering checkerboard at screen center. After the participant had fixated on the stimulus for 500 ms, the flicker ceased, and the stimulus was shifted to a lateral position. The task of the participant was to re-fixate on the laterally displaced stimulus as rapidly as possible. Upon re-fixation, the stimulus was changed into an infant face which then remained on the screen for 2000 ms. That is, in each trial the infant face stimulus became visible only after saccadic re-fixation to the checkerboard probe. However, in the course of repeated trials the participant comes to (implicitly) associate the particular location with the emotional stimulus repeatedly presented on the same

location/side of the screen (Nummenmaa et al., 2009). The task consisted of two blocks (A and B), where the position of the appearance of the infant facial expressions of emotion were varied. During block A, the SN face always appeared in the right-sided position, and during block B, it appeared in the left-sided position. MP was always presented, in randomly assigned trials, on the opposite position to that assigned to SN within each block. The order of blocks A and B was counterbalanced across participants. The task consisted of total 40 trials with a uniform distribution of SN and MP stimuli. SRT data for gaze shifts from the center to the side were extracted as mean values for SN and MP faces across locations.

In the second SRT task, “Disengagement paradigm”, participants viewed SN and MP faces in the center of the screen and were required to disengage from the face to a target stimulus (checkerboard pattern) that was presented randomly on a left or right lateral position. After 1000-ms from face onset, the target stimulus appeared with an equal probability at a left or right lateral position. The task of the participant was to shift gaze towards the lateral target as fast as possible. For each participant, both SN and MP stimuli were presented 10 times (in a total of 20 trials) in a random order.

Following the procedures used in previous studies (Leppänen et al., 2015), the SRTs from the two tasks were censored at 1000 ms, and converted to relative values in reference to the range of possible SRT values (850 ms after rejecting “anticipatory” saccades with $SRT < 150$ ms). This index combines delayed saccadic responses in the SRT range and saccade omissions, which have both been used as measures of difficulty in disengagement (Leppänen et al., 2015). We refer to the relative SRT as rSRT in the following analyses.

SES and mental health

As in Study I, SES was assessed using household income (<ZAR1,000; ZAR1,000–5,000; >ZAR5,000), maternal education (1 = primary, 2 = some secondary, 3 = completed secondary), and employment status (0 = unemployed, 1 = employed). An additional variable concerning household assets was quantified using a summary score ranging from 1 to 10. These four subdomains of SES were investigated individually as potential predictors of maternal pupillary and orientation responses.

Diagnostic interviews were performed using the MINI (Sheehan et al., 1998). Following Study I, we further included maternal self-reported measures of stressful and traumatic events [Modified LE questionnaire (Stein et al., 2015)] as well as mood and depressive symptoms [Beck Depression Inventory, BDI (Beck, Steer, & Brown, 1996)].

Statistical analyses

The relationships between eye-tracking measures, SES and mental health variables were analyzed with three stepwise hierarchical regression (SHR) analyses with the following dependent variables: 1) pupil dilation to SN faces; 2) rSRT reflecting attention orientation to location of SN face; and 3) rSRT reflecting disengagement from SN faces. For the saccade-based measures, attentional bias was quantified as the difference between SN and the MP condition. Candidate predictors for all three analyses included SES variables (family income, mother's education, employment, and assets), as well as variables related to mental health (presence of mental disorder, depression symptoms, and number of adverse life events). Based on the probability value of individual predictor coefficients, independent variables were selected to be entered ($p < .05$) or removed ($p > .10$) from the model.

Missing variables were replaced by the means of multiple imputation (IBM SPSS 25; automatic multiple imputation) using the Fully Conditional Specification Method with five imputations. Missing variables were replaced based on statistical models where model used all other variables as main effects. Scale variables (pupil and saccadic reaction measures, stressful life events, BDI, and assets) were modeled with linear regression, and categorical variables (income, education, employment, diagnoses) with logistic regression. The results were then obtained from statistics pooled across imputations for regression analyses, correlation coefficients and t-tests. Pooled one-sample t-tests, were obtained using MKmisc package for R-language.

Results

SES and mental health

The proportion of participants across the three categories of household income were 15.4% (<ZAR1,000), 54.3% (ZAR1,000–5,000), and 30.4% (>ZAR5,000), respectively ($N = 214$). The majority of mothers (96.0%) had not completed secondary education and 50.5% were unemployed.

Incidence of any mental disorder in the sample ($N = 214$) was 32.7%, including PTSD (15.4%), alcohol use disorder (14.5%), major depressive disorder (MDD; 6.1%), and anxiety disorders (2.8%). The number of traumatic life events experienced by participants ranged from 0 to 31 ($M = 7.1$, $SD = 6.5$, $N = 214$). Self-reported depression symptom score (BDI, $N = 214$) in the current sample ranged from 0 (mode) to 62 and was centered around a mean of 6.8 ($SD = 9.3$).

Among SES variables, family income correlated with employment [$r(214) = .28, p < .001$] and assets [$r(214) = .25, p < .001$]. Income and assets correlated negatively with BDI and traumatic life events [$r_s < -.15, p_s < .05$] and income with alcohol use disorder [$r(214) = -.18, p < .05$]. All pairwise correlations between independent variables are shown in Supplementary Material (Table SV).

Eye tracking measures

A clear pupil dilation response ($M = 0.02$ mm, $SD = 0.10$) was found in response to stimuli depicting infant faces with SN emotional expressions [$t(141.11) = 2.61, p < 0.05, d = 0.18$ (Table III)]. No dilation above the baseline value of pupil diameter was found in the MP condition [$t(180.91) = -1.50, p = 0.14, d = -0.10$]. Baseline-corrected pupil size was larger in the SN (0.02 mm) than in the MP (-0.01 mm) condition [$t(96) = 3.35, p < 0.001, d = 0.23$].

Relative SRT values in the spatial association and disengagement paradigms were below 30% ($SD = 12\%$) and 40% ($SD = 12\%$) of maximal values, respectively (Table III). These values correspond to censored SRTs of around 380 ms and 460 ms, respectively. In the entire sample, no difference was found in rSRT between the SN and MP condition, either when the face stimulus was presented at the lateral target location [$t = -1.10, p = 0.28, d = -0.08$] or at the central fixation [$t = 0.63, p = 0.54, d = 0.04$]. Increased pupil response to the SN face was found to correlate negatively with rSRT in the SN condition in the spatial association task [$r(214) = -.25, p < .01$].

***Please, insert Table III around here. ***

Associations with SES and psychosocial variables

For the pupil response (Figure 2), family income was identified as the only significant predictor in the stepwise hierarchical regression [$r(214) = .17$, $R^2 = .03$, $t = 2.42$, $p < .05$]. Larger response was found in highest income group (0.04 mm, $N = 65$) in comparison to the middle-income group [0.01 mm, pooled $N = 116$; $t = 2.14$, $p < .05$] and the lowest income group [-0.01 mm, pooled $N = 33$; $t = 2.18$, $p < .05$]. No difference was found between the middle and the lowest income groups [$t = 0.74$, $p < .47$]. In separate analyses within each group, increased pupil dilation in SN vs. MP condition was found only in the highest income group ($t = 3.67$, $p < .001$, $d = 0.46$). First-order bivariate correlations between independent and dependent variables, as well as the descriptive statistics of independent variables, are indicated in Table IV.

***Please, insert Table IV around here. ***

The bias to shift gaze faster to locations cued by SN affect was predicted by sets of variables selected by stepwise hierarchical regression [$F_s > 5.39$, $p_s < .01$]. The following predictors were found across imputed datasets: family income, employment, number of traumatic life events, MDD, and BDI. Only family income was found to correlate with cued saccadic latency [$r(214) = -.19$, $p < .05$] in analysis of pooled correlations across multiple imputations. The saccadic reactions to emotionally cued locations decreased in latency with increasing family income (Figure 3). This difference in rSRT between SN and MP conditions was largest in the group with highest family income (0.04, pooled $N = 65$), followed by the middle-income group (0.01, pooled $N = 116$; group difference $t = 1.39$, $p < .18$), and the lowest-income group (-0.02, pooled $N = 33$; $t = 2.24$, $p < .05$). The difference in rSRT between SN and MP conditions was significantly different from zero only in the highest income group ($t = -1.78$, $p < .05$, $d = -0.22$).

For the gaze disengagement score, several predictor variables were found across stepwise hierarchical regression analysis across imputed datasets including education, employment, assets, PTSD, alcohol dependency and BDI ($F_s > 5.99$, $p_s < .05$). However, no significant pairwise associations were found between disengagement latency and these predictors in correlations pooled across multiple imputations ($|r|s < .11$, $p_s > .17$).

***Please, insert Figure 3 around here. ***

Discussion

Our results from two independent studies showed that the known enhancement of maternal physiological responses and orientation of attention to infant distress cues varies by socioeconomic status as indexed by household income in a heterogeneous community sample from South Africa. We found no evidence for an association between responsiveness to infant cues and maternal mental disorders.

Previous research has shown enhanced attentional capture (Thompson-Booth et al., 2014) and neural activation (Proverbio, De Gabriele, Manfredi, & Adorni, 2011; Riem et al., 2017a; Riem, van IJzendoorn et al., 2017b) to infant as compared to adult faces. These responses are further enhanced by infant facial expressions of emotion as indicated by comparisons between emotional and neutral expressions and those between negative vs. positive expressions (Peltola et al., 2014; Proverbio et al., 2006; Thompson-Booth et al., 2014; Yrttiaho et al., 2017). This enhancement is more pronounced in mothers than in non-parent adults (Peltola et al., 2014; Proverbio et al., 2006; Thompson-Booth et al., 2014). Studies examining individual differences in this responsivity have shown that maladaptive parenting practices are associated with overactive reactivity to infant distress (Frodi & Lamb, 1980; Joosen et al., 2013; Leerkes et al., 2015), suggesting there might be an optimum level of arousal for maternal care between the excessively low and high values. Based on these findings, we expected that mothers with psychiatric disorders might have propensity for impeded or overactive pupillary or attentional responses to infant cues of distress. In contrast, no direct associations between mental health status and responsiveness were found in the current results. In Study I, the mental disorders were more prevalent in the low-SES group where the emotional pupil response to infant faces was found to be decreased in comparison to the high-SES group. While this might suggest a mediation of the effects of socioeconomic status through mental health, this interpretation was

challenged by lack of correlation between mental illness and pupil response within the participant groups.

Study II, using multivariate analysis of SES and mental health, corroborated our initial finding of SES, but not mental health, as a significant predictor of pupil as well as attentional responsiveness to infant cues of distress. This finding is consistent with recent results from neuroimaging studies that associate low SES with decreased activation of prefrontal areas involved in the regulation of attention and emotion (Kim et al., 2016). The existence of a similar association with SES in two samples that varied in ethnicity supports the generalizability of this association, but it is important to note that SES is often intertwined with variations in several sociocultural factors that may be difficult to disentangle and were not all controlled for in the present analyses. Based on current data it is, therefore, impossible to distinguish the independent effects of SES from other sociocultural factors (e.g., behavioral patterns, values, norms, and ideals) that are correlated with SES (Kraus et al., 2011) or those that might influence the appraisal of mental health status (Qureshi, Collazos, Ramos, & Casas, 2008).

Diminished pupil and attentional responses to infant distress may be explained by a number of sociocultural and behavioral aspects that covary with low SES. Recent research (Keller et al., 2018) suggests that parental responsiveness to infant cues, especially to visual signals in distal face-to-face interaction, is strongly dependent on sociocultural context. These sociocultural and economic differences in parenting style, including sensitivity, may persist throughout motherhood (Brooks-Gunn & Markman, 2005). Parallel evidence suggests that forms of social behavior beyond parenting (e.g. returning a lost letter) also tend to vary by socioeconomic context, and that these behaviors tend to be less frequent in low-income residential neighborhoods (Holland et al., 2012; Nettle et al., 2011). It is possible, therefore, that the enhanced maternal responsiveness to visual cues of infant distress as compared to neutral or

positive comparison stimuli, as documented in the current study and in previous studies using similar methods (Joosen et al., 2013; Leerkes et al., 2015; Pearson, Cooper, Penton-Voak, Lightman, & Evans, 2010; Thompson-Booth et al., 2014; Yrttiaho et al., 2017), may not be as universal as often assumed (Preston, 2013) and may be subject to important sociocultural variations that are, in part, captured by objective indicators SES.

An alternative possibility is that the responsiveness to infant cues is a universal trait, but the expression of this trait is subject to variability due to an interfering effect of different SES-related factors. For example, responsiveness and cognitive capacity may be depleted by preoccupation with poverty in low-income populations, or by experiences of stressors and lack of support (Goldstein, Diener, & Mangelsdorf, 1996). Parts of the neural network that are relevant for pupil and attentional responses (i.e., the amygdala and its connections with the LC-NE arousal system) are sensitive to stress (Aston-Jones & Cohen, 2005; Joshi et al., 2016; Noble, Houston, Kan, & Sowell, 2012; Reimer et al., 2014; Sara & Bouret, 2012), and there is evidence for compensatory hypoactivation of arousal to socio-emotional signals and impaired focused attention in prolonged activation of the stress system (Benarroch, 2009; Pervanidou, 2008). Second, poverty-related concerns, independently of stress or other immediate mediating factors (e.g., nutrition or work effort), have further been suggested to consume mental resources leading to diminished cognitive capacity (Mani, Mullainathan, Shafir, & Zhao, 2013). Thus, it might be speculated that sensitivity to infant signals is impeded by preoccupation with poverty, similarly to experiences of lack of support and stress (Goldstein et al., 1996). However, it seems unlikely that the variability in responsiveness to infant cues in the current study is related to factors that deplete cognitive capacity, as we found no associations between physiological responsiveness and various (capacity-depleting) mental health conditions (Feldman et al., 2009; Leppänen et al., 2006; Sloan, Bradley, Dimoulas, & Lang, 2002). It is not clear however, whether this lack of association would generalize to more homogenous samples that have a

larger and more representative group of individuals with a particular psychiatric profile (Cascardi et al., 2015; Joosen et al., 2013; Kimble et al., 2010; Leerkes et al., 2015). It is also possible that the associations in the current study were affected by sociocultural differences in self-reported psychiatric symptoms or psychiatric evaluations (Qureshi et al., 2008).

The bias for infant distress was seen in pupil and attentional orienting responses but not in measures of attention disengagement. Based on theories of emotionally driven attention (Bar-Haim, Lamy, Pergamin, Bakermans-Kranenburg, & van IJzendoorn, 2007), we would have predicted that the bias for distress manifests as a combination of both fast orientation and slow disengagement. While we did see evidence for preferential orientation of attention to distressed faces among the high-SES participants, we did not find the predicted delays in disengagement from distress cues for any of the participant groups. It is therefore possible that the instruction to voluntarily disengage from the faces overcame potential biases in attention orientation in the latter task.

In addition to limitations in interpreting the associations with SES, this study had other methodological limitations. The study lacked direct measures of parental attachment behaviors apart from self-reported bonding questionnaires. While previous studies using physiological and electrocortical measures have found associations between maternal responsiveness to infant distress cues and observed maternal sensitivity (Joosen et al., 2013; Kim, Capistrano, Erhart, Gray-Schiff, & Xu, 2017; Leerkes et al., 2015), the degree to which the currently observed pupil and attentional responses relate to everyday mother-infant interaction remains to be established. A potential limitation of the current study is also that stimuli had limited ethnic diversity.

In conclusion, our results replicate previous research in showing a pattern of heightened autonomic responses (pupil dilation) and attention in mothers to visual cues of infant distress

as opposed to neutral or positive affect. However, the results extend the literature in novel directions by showing the phenomenon in a unique sample and by examining how enhanced responsivity to infant distress is associated with SES and mental disorders. Our findings indicate that this response may be more context-dependent than some have posited, as indicated by the absence of the response in the lowest socioeconomic strata, and the presence of the response in some, but not all, attentional processes. Our findings have implications for the interpretation of the allegedly fundamental and universal processes related to responsiveness to conspecific distress in infant-parent communication. They motivate research examining these processes as well as their impact on child development and well-being as context-dependent phenomena.

References

- Aston-Jones, G., & Cohen, J. D. (2005). An integrative theory of locus coeruleus-norepinephrine function: Adaptive gain and optimal performance. *Annual Review of Neuroscience, 28*, 403-450.
doi:10.1146/annurev.neuro.28.061604.135709
- Bannerman, R. L., Milders, M., & Sahraie, A. (2009). Processing emotional stimuli: Comparison of saccadic and manual choice-reaction times. *Cognition and Emotion, 23*(5), 930-954.
- Bar-Haim, Y., Lamy, D., Pergamin, L., Bakermans-Kranenburg, M., & van IJzendoorn, M. H. (2007). Threat-related attentional bias in anxious and nonanxious individuals: A meta-analytic study. *Psychological Bulletin, 133*(1), 1-24.
- Barrett, J., & Fleming, A. S. (2011). Annual research review: All mothers are not created equal: Neural and psychobiological perspectives on mothering and the importance of individual differences. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry, and Allied Disciplines, 52*(4), 368-397.
doi:10.1111/j.1469-7610.2010.02306.x
- Beck, A. T., Steer, R. A., & Brown, G. K. (1996). Beck depression inventory-II. *San Antonio, 78*(2), 490-498.
- Benarroch, E. E. (2009). The locus ceruleus norepinephrine system: Functional organization and potential clinical significance. *Neurology, 73*(20), 1699-1704.
doi:10.1212/WNL.0b013e3181c2937c
- Bornstein, M. H., Putnick, D. L., Park, Y., Suwalsky, J. T., & Haynes, O. M. (2017). Human infancy and parenting in global perspective: Specificity. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences, 284*(1869), 20172168.
- Brooks-Gunn, J., & Markman, L. B. (2005). The contribution of parenting to ethnic and racial gaps in school readiness. *The Future of Children, 15*, 139-168.

- Brugha, T., Bebington, P., Tennant, C., & Hurry, J. (1985). The list of threatening experiences: A subset of 12 life events categories with considerable long-term contextual threat. *Psychological Medicine, 15*, 189-194.
- Cascardi, M., Armstrong, D., Chung, L., & Paré, D. (2015). Pupil response to threat in trauma-exposed individuals with or without PTSD. *Journal of Traumatic Stress, 28*(4), 370-374.
- Choi, S. K., Kim, J. J., Park, Y. G., Ko, H. S., Park, I. Y., & Shin, J. C. (2012). The simplified Edinburgh postnatal depression scale (EPDS) for antenatal depression: Is it a valid measure for pre-screening? *International Journal of Medical Sciences, 9*(1), 40-46.
- Colasante, T., Mossad, S. I., Dudek, J., & Haley, D. W. (2017). The special status of sad infant faces: Age and valence differences in adults' cortical face processing. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience, 12*(4), 586-595.
- Dawson, N., Bain, K., & Mesman, J. (2018). Comparing two measures of maternal sensitivity: Goodness of fit with a South African cultural context. *Attachment & Human Development, 28*(1), 1-9.
- Du Toit, E., Jordaan, E., Niehaus, D., Koen, L., & Leppanen, J. (2018). Risk factors for unplanned pregnancy in women with mental illness living in a developing country. *Archives of Women's Mental Health, 21*(3), 323-331.
- Eisenberg, N., & Eggum, N. D. (2008). Empathy-related and prosocial responding: Conceptions and correlates during development. In B. A. Sullivan, M. Snyder, & J. L. Sullivan (Eds.), *Cooperation: The political psychology of effective human interaction* (p. 53–74). Blackwell Publishing.
- Feldman, R. (2007). Parent–infant synchrony and the construction of shared timing; physiological precursors, developmental outcomes, and risk conditions. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry, 48*(3-4), 329-354.

- Frodi, A. M., & Lamb, M. E. (1980). Child abusers' responses to infant smiles and cries. *Child Development, 51*(1), 238-241.
- Goldstein, L. H., Diener, M. L., & Mangelsdorf, S. C. (1996). Maternal characteristics and social support across the transition to motherhood: Associations with maternal behavior. *Journal of Family Psychology, 10*(1), 60.
- Granholm, E., Ruiz, I., Gallegos-Rodriguez, Y., Holden, J., & Link, P. C. (2016). Pupillary responses as a biomarker of diminished effort associated with defeatist attitudes and negative symptoms in schizophrenia. *Biological Psychiatry, 80*(8), 581-588.
- Henrich, J., Heine, S. J., & Norenzayan, A. (2010). The weirdest people in the world? *Behavioral and Brain Sciences, 33*(2-3), 61-83.
- Holland, J., Silva, A. S., & Mace, R. (2012). Lost letter measure of variation in altruistic behaviour in 20 neighbourhoods. *Plos One, 7*(8), e43294.
- Hood, B. M., & Atkinson, J. (1993). Disengaging visual attention in the infant and adult. *Infant Behavior and Development, 16*(4), 405-422.
- Hruschka, D. J., Munira, S., Jesmin, K., Hackman, J., & Tiokhin, L. (2018). Learning from failures of protocol in cross-cultural research. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 115*(45), 11428-11434.
- Joosen, K. J., Mesman, J., Bakermans-Kranenburg, M., & van Ijzendoorn, M. H. (2013). Maternal overreactive sympathetic nervous system responses to repeated infant crying predicts risk for impulsive harsh discipline of infants. *Child Maltreatment, 18*(4), 252-263.
- Joshi, S., Li, Y., Kalwani, R. M., & Gold, J. I. (2016). Relationships between pupil diameter and neuronal activity in the locus coeruleus, colliculi, and cingulate cortex. *Neuron, 89*(1), 221-234.
doi:10.1016/j.neuron.2015.11.028

- Keller, H., Bard, K., Morelli, G., Chaudhary, N., Vicedo, M., Rosabal-Coto, M., . . . Gottlieb, A. (2018). The myth of universal sensitive responsiveness: Comment on Mesman et al. (2017). *Child Development, 89*, 1921-1928.
- Kim, P., Capistrano, C. G., Erhart, A., Gray-Schiff, R., & Xu, N. (2017). Socioeconomic disadvantage, neural responses to infant emotions, and emotional availability among first-time new mothers. *Behavioural Brain Research, 325*, 188-196.
- Kim, P., Capistrano, C., & Congleton, C. (2016). Socioeconomic disadvantages and neural sensitivity to infant cry: Role of maternal distress. *Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience, 11*(10), 1597-1607.
- Kimble, M. O., Fleming, K., Bandy, C., Kim, J., & Zambetti, A. (2010). Eye tracking and visual attention to threatening stimuli in veterans of the iraq war. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders, 24*(3), 293-299.
- Kraus, M. W., Piff, P. K., & Keltner, D. (2011). Social class as culture: The convergence of resources and rank in the social realm. *Current Directions in Psychological Science, 20*(4), 246-250.
- Laeng, B., Sirois, S., & Gredeback, G. (2012). Pupillometry: A window to the preconscious? *Perspectives on Psychological Science, 7*(1), 18-27. doi:doi: 10.1177/1745691611427305
- Leclère, C., Viaux, S., Avril, M., Achard, C., Chetouani, M., Missonnier, S., & Cohen, D. (2014). Why synchrony matters during mother-child interactions: A systematic review. *PloS One, 9*(12), e113571.
- Leerkes, E. M., Supple, A. J., O'Brien, M., Calkins, S. D., Haltigan, J. D., Wong, M. S., & Fortuna, K. (2015). Antecedents of maternal sensitivity during distressing tasks: Integrating attachment, social information processing, and psychobiological perspectives. *Child Development, 86*(1), 94-111.

- Leppänen, J. M., Forssman, L., Kaatiala, J., Yrttiaho, S., & Wass, S. (2015). Widely applicable MATLAB routines for automated analysis of saccadic reaction times. *Behavior Research Methods*, *47*(2), 538-548. doi:10.3758/s13428-014-0473-z
- Leppänen, J. M., Peltola, M. J., Puura, K., Mäntymaa, M., Mononen, N., & Lehtimäki, T. (2011). Serotonin and early cognitive development: Variation in the tryptophan hydroxylase 2 gene is associated with visual attention in 7-month-old infants. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, *52*, 1144-1152.
- Mani, A., Mullainathan, S., Shafir, E., & Zhao, J. (2013). Poverty impedes cognitive function. *Science*, *341*(6149), 976-980. doi:10.1126/science.1238041
- Mesman, J. (2018). Sense and sensitivity: A response to the commentary by Keller et al. (2018). *Child Development*, *89*(5), 1929-1931.
- Morelli, G., Quinn, N., Chaudhary, N., Vicedo, M., Rosabal-Coto, M., Keller, H., . . . Takada, A. (2018). Ethical challenges of parenting interventions in low- to middle-income countries. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, *49*(1), 5-24.
- Naegeli, C., Zeffiro, T., Piccirelli, M., Jaillard, A., Weilenmann, A., Hassanpour, K., . . . Mueller-Pfeiffer, C. (2018). Locus coeruleus activity mediates hyperresponsiveness in posttraumatic stress disorder. *Biological Psychiatry*, *83*(3), 254-262.
- Nelson, C. A., Zeanah, C. H., Fox, N. A., Marshall, P. J., Smyke, A. T., & Guthrie, D. (2007). Cognitive recovery in socially deprived young children: The Bucharest early intervention project. *Science*, *318*(5858), 1937-1940. doi:10.1126/science.1143921
- Nettle, D., Colléony, A., & Cockerill, M. (2011). Variation in cooperative behaviour within a single city. *Plos One*, *6*(10), e26922.
- Noble, K. G., Houston, S. M., Kan, E., & Sowell, E. R. (2012). Neural correlates of socioeconomic status in the developing human brain. *Developmental Science*, *15*(4), 516-527.

- Nummenmaa, L., Hyönä, J., & Calvo, M. G. (2009). Emotional scene content drives the saccade generation system reflexively. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, *35*(2), 305.
- Pearson, R. M., Cooper, R. M., Penton-Voak, I., Lightman, S. L., & Evans, J. (2010). Depressive symptoms in early pregnancy disrupt attentional processing of infant emotion. *Psychological Medicine*, *40*(4), 621-631.
- Peltola, M. J., Yrttiaho, S., Puura, K., Proverbio, A. M., Mononen, N., Lehtimäki, T., & Leppänen, J. M. (2014). Motherhood and oxytocin receptor genetic variation are associated with selective changes in electrocortical responses to infant facial expressions. *Emotion*, *14*(3), 469-477.
- Pervanidou, P. (2008). Biology of post-traumatic stress disorder in childhood and adolescence. *Journal of Neuroendocrinology*, *20*(5), 632-638.
- Preston, S. D. (2013). The origins of altruism in offspring care. *Psychological Bulletin*, *139*(6), 1305.
- Proverbio, A. M., Brignone, V., Matarazzo, S., Del Zotto, M., & Zani, A. (2006). Gender and parental status affect the visual cortical response to infant facial expression. *Neuropsychologia*, *44*(14), 2987-2999.
- Proverbio, A. M., De Gabriele, V., Manfredi, M., & Adorni, R. (2011). No race effect (ORE) in the automatic orienting toward baby faces: When ethnic group does not matter. *Psychology*, *2*(9), 931-935.
- Proverbio, A. M., Matarazzo, S., Brignone, V., Del Zotto, M., & Zani, A. (2007). Processing valence and intensity of infant expressions: The roles of expertise and gender. *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology*, *48*, 477-485.
- Qureshi, A., Collazos, F., Ramos, M., & Casas, M. (2008). Cultural competency training in psychiatry. *European Psychiatry*, *23*, 49-58.

- Reimer, J., Froudarakis, E., Cadwell, C. R., Yatsenko, D., Denfield, G. H., & Tolia, A. S. (2014). Pupil fluctuations track fast switching of cortical states during quiet wakefulness. *Neuron*, *84*(2), 355-362.
- Riem, M. M., van IJzendoorn, M. H., De Carli, P., Vingerhoets, A. J., & Bakermans-Kranenburg, M. J. (2017a). Behavioral and neural responses to infant and adult tears: The impact of maternal love withdrawal. *Emotion*, *17*(6), 1021.
- Riem, M. M., van IJzendoorn, M., De Carli, P., Vingerhoets, A., & Bakermans-Kranenburg, M. (2017b). As tears go by: Baby tears trigger more brain activity than adult tears in nulliparous women. *Social Neuroscience*, *12*(6), 633-636.
- Sara, S. J., & Bouret, S. (2012). Orienting and reorienting: The locus coeruleus mediates cognition through arousal. *Neuron*, *76*(1), 130-141.
- Sheehan, D. V., Lecrubier, Y., Sheehan, K. H., Amorim, P., Janavs, J., Weiller, E., . . . Dunbar, G. C. (1998). The mini-international neuropsychiatric interview (M.I.N.I.): The development and validation of a structured diagnostic psychiatric interview for DSM-IV and ICD-10. *The Journal of Clinical Psychiatry*, *59 Suppl 20*, 2-57.
- Siegle, G. J., Granholm, E., Ingram, R. E., & Matt, G. E. (2001). Pupillary and reaction time measures of sustained processing of negative information in depression. *Biological Psychiatry*, *49*(7), 624-636.
- Stein, D. J., Koen, N., Donald, K. A., Adnams, C. M., Koopowitz, S., Lund, C., . . . Sorsdahl, K. (2015). Investigating the psychosocial determinants of child health in Africa: The Drakenstein Child Health Study. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*, *252*, 27-35.
- Taylor, Z. E., & Conger, R. D. (2017). Promoting strengths and resilience in single-mother families. *Child Development*, *88*(2), 350-358.

Thompson-Booth, C., Viding, E., Mayes, L. C., Rutherford, H. J. V., Hodsoll, S., & McCrory, E. J. (2014).

Here's looking at you, kid: Attention to infant emotional faces in mothers and non-mothers.

Developmental Science, 17(1), 35-46.

Van Bussel, J. C. H., Spitz, B., & Demyttenaere, K. (2010). Three self-report questionnaires of the early

mother-to-infant bond: Reliability and validity of the Dutch version of the MPAS, PBQ and MIBS.

Archives of Women's Mental Health, 13(5), 373-384.

Wainstein, G., Rojas-Libano, D., Crossley, N., Carrasco, X., Aboitiz, F., & Ossandón, T. (2017). Pupil size

tracks attentional performance in attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder. *Scientific Reports*,

7(1), 1-9.

Wang, C. A., Boehnke, S. E., White, B. J., & Munoz, D. P. (2012). Microstimulation of the monkey

superior colliculus induces pupil dilation without evoking saccades. *The Journal of Neuroscience* :

The Official Journal of the Society for Neuroscience, 32(11), 3629-3636.

doi:10.1523/JNEUROSCI.5512-11.2012

Yrttiaho, S., Niehaus, D., Thomas, E., & Leppänen, J. M. (2017). Mothers' pupillary responses to infant

facial expressions. *Behavioral and Brain Functions : BBF*, 13(1), 9. doi:10.1186/s12993-017-0120-

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Figure captions

Figure 1. Categories of stimuli used in Studies I (top) and II (bottom). In Study I, four different categories of facial expressions were used and the prestimulus image was constructed by randomly permuting the pixels from all face stimuli. In Study II, two categories of facial stimuli were used and prestimulus image was matched to the face stimuli with respect to the luminance profile of the stimulus.

Figure 2. Grand average pupil waveform in response to infant face stimuli. a) Study I. Pupil response from participant mothers recruited via public ($N = 53$) and private ($N = 58$) well-baby clinics, described by low and high SES, respectively. b) Study II. Pupil response from the lowest ($N = 24$) and highest income group ($N = 39$). MN = mild negative, MP = mild positive, SN = strong negative, and SP = strong positive. Shaded area around pupil waveform indicates standard error of mean $\times 2$.

Figure 3. Attention orientation towards locations cued with infant face stimuli with strong negative (SN) or mild positive (MP) facial expressions. Confidence intervals indicate standard errors of mean values.

Tables

Table I. Demographic variables across sampled public and private health care sites in Study I.

SES variables are indicated as frequencies and percentages in parentheses. Differences between sites: *** $p < .001$

		Public	Private	Total
Age, years***	Mean (SD)	30.4 (6.3)	34.4 (4.1)	32.5 (5.6)
Family income***	< R10K	41 (77.4%)	3 (5.2%)	44
	R10K-20K	8 (15.1%)	4 (6.9%)	12
	R20K-40K	4 (7.5%)	10 (17.2%)	14
	> R40K	0 (0%)	41 (70.7%)	41
Employment***	Employed	2 (3.8%)	0 (0%)	2
	Unemployed	47 (88.7%)	4 (6.9%)	51
	Housewife	0 (0%)	4 (6.9%)	4
	Maternity leave	4 (7.5%)	48 (82.8%)	52
	Self-employed	0 (0%)	2 (3.4%)	2
Education***	Low	47 (88.7%)	3 (5.2%)	50
	High	6 (11.3%)	55 (94.8%)	61
Total N		53 (100%)	58 (100%)	111

Table II. Mental health and socioemotional problems across sampled public and private health care sites in Study I. Differences between sites: † $p < .10$, * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$.

		Public	Private	Total
Mental illness*	Frequency (%)	19 (35.8%)	9 (15.5%)	28
EPDS ≥ 12 **	Frequency (%)	14 (26.4%)	3 (5.2%)	17
MIBS†	Mean (SD)	2.1 (4.0)	1.1 (1.8)	1.6 (3.1)
MPAS	Mean (SD)	84.7 (13.8)	84.6 (7.3)	84.7 (10.8)
PBQ	Mean (SD)	11.8 (14.7)	9.6 (8.2)	10.6 (11.8)
RLEQ, happened**	Mean (SD)	4.3 (3.7)	2.6 (2.1)	3.4 (3.1)
RLEQ, still affecting	Mean (SD)	1.3 (3.4)	0.6 (1.1)	1.0 (2.5)

Table III. Mean values and standard deviation of eye tracking variables in Study II (N = 214 after multiple imputation). Pupil response was found to differ from zero in the SN condition, * $p < .01$. SN = strong negative, MP = mild positive.

	Mean	SD
Pupil dilation		
SN	0.02*	0.10
MP	-0.01	0.09
rSRT, Spatial association task		
SN	.27	.14
MP	.28	.14
rSRT, Disengagement		
SN	.37	.32
MP	.37	.34

Table IV. Correlation of predictor variables to pupil response and relative saccadic reaction time (rSRT, difference between strong negative and mild negative condition), and descriptive statistics of the predictors included in the stepwise hierarchical regression analyses in Study II (N = 214). *Correlation differs from zero: $p < .05$.

	Correlation to pupil response		Correlation to rSRT		Descriptives	
	r	p	r	p	Mean	Min-Max
Income	.17*	< .05	-.19*	< .05	2.15	1-3
Education	-.08	.23	-.05	.56	1.17	1-3
Assets	-.01	.89	-.09	.29	6.07	1-10
Work	.07	.34	-.15	.06	.48	0-1
BDI	-.01	.92	.10	.25	6.03	0-62
Stressful events	-.06	.43	.14	.07	6.42	0-31
PTSD	.01	.87	-.03	.75	.16	0-1
MDD	.08	.28	-.09	.29	.06	0-1
Alcohol abuse	.02	.80	.08	.47	.14	0-1

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3